

Studies on Hydrrous Zirconium Oxide. Part-II†. Electrophoretic Behaviour of Metal Ions on Hydrrous Zirconium Oxide impregnated Papers

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Electrophoresis of 21 metal ions on hydrrous zirconium oxide impregnated papers have been carried out. Five background electrolytes were used at fixed voltages and time intervals. On the basis of the differential mobilities of the ions, which depends on the ion-exchange properties of hydrrous zirconium oxide and the nature of the complexes formed with the electrolytes, some useful binary and ternary separations have been achieved.

THE importance of synthetic inorganic ion-exchangers in the field of separation science has been reviewed¹⁻⁴. Papers impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers have been extensively used for chromatographic separation of metal ions. Electrophoresis of metal ions on paper impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers plays an important role in separation science. Alberti *et al.*⁵ separated La⁺⁺⁺, Pr⁺⁺⁺ and Sm⁺⁺⁺ by this technique using zirconium phosphate papers. Some electrophoretic studies with synthetic inorganic ion-exchangers have been reported⁶⁻⁹. Highly selective separations of metal ions were observed. ZrO₂·xH₂O acts as a cation-exchanger at higher pH. In this paper, electrophoretic behaviour of some metal ions on hydrrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper is discussed. In order to determine the role of the ion-exchanger in these studies, the same operation was repeated with ordinary Whatman no. 1 paper. Some difficult and interesting separations have been achieved. The survey of literature reveals that no such work has been reported earlier.

Experimental

Electrophoresis was carried out in a Optronics EPR 550 horizontal apparatus.

All reagents were of E. Merck or B.D.H. analytical reagent grade. Whatman no. 1 chromatographic paper (40×2.5 cm) was used for electrophoretic work.

Preparation of hydrrous zirconium oxide impregnated papers: Paper strips were first soaked with freshly prepared 0.1 M aqueous solution of zirconyl

chloride in 0.1 M HCl for 10 s and the excess being removed by blotting, and the strips dried at room temperature. The dried strips were then passed through 1 M aqueous ammonia solution for 10 s and the excess removed by blotting and then dried horizontally at 100±5° for 1 h in an air-oven. Ordinary Whatman paper strips were also dried in an air-oven at 100±5° for 1 h for better comparison. The dried papers were washed several times with double-distilled water and finally dried at room temperature before use.

Cation solutions: Solutions of the nitrate, sulphate or chloride of most of the cations were prepared (metal ion 2-4 mg ml⁻¹) in water. Bismuth nitrate solution was prepared in dilute nitric acid. Platinum solutions was prepared by dissolving chloroplatinic acid in water.

Background electrolytes: Five aqueous background electrolyte solutions were used for electrophoretic work: (i) 0.05 M HCl+0.09 M KCl (pH 2), (ii) 0.2 M CH₃COOH+0.2 M CH₃COONa (pH 4), (iii) 0.1 M CH₃COOH + 0.1 M CH₃COONa (pH 6), (iv) 0.1 M NH₄OH+0.1 M NH₄Cl (pH 8), and (v) 0.1 M NH₄OH+0.1 M NH₄Cl (pH 10).

Detection reagents: The following detection reagents were used: (i) yellow ammonium sulphide solution: Pb⁺⁺, Ag⁺, Hg⁺⁺, Hg₂⁺⁺, Bi⁺⁺⁺, Tl⁺, Cu⁺⁺, Pd⁺⁺, (ii) aqueous K₄[Fe(CN)₆] (saturated): Fe⁺⁺⁺, UO₂⁺⁺, (iii) 0.05% benzidine in 10% acetic acid: Mn⁺⁺, Au⁺⁺⁺, (iv) dithiozone (1-2 mg) in 100 ml CCl₄: Cd⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺, (v) ammonium thiocyanate in acetone (saturated): Co⁺⁺, (vi) 1%

† Part I, Ref. 10.

ethanolic dimethyl glyoxime : Ni²⁺, (vii) 5% KI solution : Pt²⁺, (viii) 0.2% rubeanic acid : Ru²⁺, and (ix) SnCl₂ in dilute HCl+KI : Rh²⁺.

Procedure : The electrode vessels were washed with distilled water, dried in air and filled with equal volumes (300 ml) of background electrolyte solution. The centres of the strips were marked with pencil and the strips soaked with the corresponding background electrolyte, the excess being removed by blotting. The strips were placed horizontally in the cassette. A drop of individual metal ion solution was placed in the middle of each strip separately by glass capillary. The cassette was then covered and a potential of about 250 V was applied for 2 h. The migration of zones of ions was measured from the point of application to the middle of the zone. On the basis of the results observed in the case of individual metal ions, the experiment was repeated with synthetic binary or ternary mixture of the particular metal ions of interest.

Results and Discussion

Electrophoresis is based on the differential migration of charged particles in an electrical field. The distance of the centre of zone from the middle of the paper where the metal ion was originally spotted is given in cm with a negative sign indicating movement of the ion towards the cathode and a positive sign used for the distance travelled

towards the anode, while ions which do not show any movement are marked 0.00. The electrophoretic behaviour of 21 metal ions on hydrous zirconium oxide papers and on ordinary Whatman no. 1 papers has been studied using five background electrolytes of different pH. The results are given in Table 1. The migration distances on ordinary Whatman no. 1 papers are given in parenthesis in Table 1. The rate of migration on an impregnated paper under a given potential difference depends on the size and charge of the components, relative molecular mass, electrolyte concentration and adsorption on the exchanger (hydrous zirconium oxide). The cation-exchange property of hydrous zirconium oxide increases with the increase in pH. This property of the exchanger is evident in the smooth decrease of movement of Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Fe²⁺ with increase of pH of the background electrolytes. In case of other cations, interactions of background electrolytes with the cations confused the system. It is interesting to note that Hg²⁺, Hg₂²⁺, Pt²⁺, Au³⁺ and Ru²⁺ behave as their corresponding anionic species in presence of all the background electrolytes of different pH. Among the metal ions, the higher movement of Hg²⁺ and Hg₂²⁺ ions on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper proves that cellulose has a strong affinity for mercury which is greatly reduced due to the presence of zirconium oxide on the surface of papers. The rate of movement of metal ions which are strongly adsorbed by the exchanger, *e.g.*

TABLE 1—MOVEMENT (cm*) OF IONS IN VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES ON HYDROUS ZIRCONIUM OXIDE PAPERS

Time = 2 h, Voltage applied = 250 V

Metal ion	0.09 M KCl + 0.05 M HCl pH 2	0.2 M CH ₃ COOH + 0.2 M CH ₃ COONa pH 4	0.1 M CH ₃ COOH + 0.1 M CH ₃ COONa pH 6	0.1 M NH ₄ OH + 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl pH 8	0.1 M NH ₄ OH + 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl pH 10
Ag ⁺	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Bi ²⁺	+1.0 (+1.5)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Pb ²⁺	-0.5 (-1.5)	-0.8 (-4.5)	0.0 (-0.3)	-0.5 (-0.8)	0.0 (0.0)
Hg ²⁺	+5.0 (+4.0)	+5.6 (+0.8)	+2.8 (0.0)	+4.0 (+2.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Pt ²⁺	+4.5 (+4.5)	+6.0 (+14.0)	+4.0 (+7.5)	+3.9 (+5.0)	+1.6 (+3.0)
Au ³⁺	+3.0 (+3.5)	+1.4 (+2.0)	0.0 (+3.6)	+0.5 (+0.5)	0.0 (+1.0)
Ni ²⁺	-2.8 (-3.2)	-2.5 (-3.5)	-2.0 (-2.0)	-3.6 (-5.5)	-1.8 (-6.0)
Co ²⁺	-2.5 (-3.5)	0.0 (-1.0)	-1.7 (-2.8)	-2.5 (-6.0)	-1.0 (T)
Cu ²⁺	-2.0 (-4.0)	-1.2 (-2.8)	0.0 (0.0)	T (-1.5)	-1.7 (-4.0)
Mn ²⁺	-1.0 (-1.6)	-3.4 (-6.0)	-2.2 (-3.5)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
UO ₂ ²⁺	-1.6 (-1.6)	+0.5 (+3.0)	+0.6 (+2.4)	T (T)	0.0 (+0.5)
Ru ²⁺	+0.3 (+0.3)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (+1.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Cr ²⁺	-1.0 (-0.9)	-	-	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
VO ²⁺	0.0 (-1.1)	0.0 (+1.2)	0.0 (+2.8)	0.0 (+2.2)	0.0 (+2.0)
Rh ²⁺	-1.8 (-0.8)	0.0 (+0.4)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Zn ²⁺	D	-2.2 (-2.5)	-0.5 (-1.2)	T (T)	T (T)
Fe ²⁺	-1.5 (-2.1)	-0.5 (-2.5)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Tl ⁺	0.0 (+1.0)	T (-13)	-5.0 (-8.5)	-3.5 (-9.0)	-2.0 (-3.5)
Hg ₂ ²⁺	+1.2 (0.0)	+0.8 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Cd ²⁺	0.0 (+0.8)	-0.5 (-5.0)	0.0 (-1.0)	-2.0 (-2.8)	0.0 (0.0)
Ce ²⁺	-1.0 (-1.5)	-2.6 (-3.3)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Pd ²⁺	0.0 (+1.5)	-3.8 (T)	-5.4 (T)	-3.2 (-6.9)	-5.0 (-5.0)

*Movement on ordinary Whatman no. 1 paper in parenthesis.

T = Tailing. D = Diffuse.

TABLE 2—BINARY AND TERNARY SEPARATIONS OF METAL IONS ON HYDROUS ZIRCONIUM OXIDE IMPREGNATED PAPER

Time - 2 h, Voltage applied - 250 V

Background electrolyte	Separations achieved*
0.05 M HCl + 0.09 M KCl (pH 2)	VO ²⁺ (0.0) - Ce ³⁺ (-1.0)/Mn ²⁺ (0.9) - Ni ²⁺ (-2.8)/Co ²⁺ (-2.5) Cd ²⁺ (0.0) - Ce ³⁺ (-1.1)/Mn ²⁺ (-1.1) - Ni ²⁺ (-2.8)/Co ²⁺ (-2.4) Tl ⁺ (0.0) - Ce ³⁺ (-1.2)/Mn ²⁺ (-1.1) - Ni ²⁺ (-2.6)/Co ²⁺ (-2.4) Pd ²⁺ (0.0) - Ce ³⁺ (-0.9)/Mn ²⁺ (-1.0) - Ni ²⁺ (-2.9)/Co ²⁺ (-2.5)
0.2 M CH ₃ COOH + 0.2 M CH ₃ COONa (pH 4)	Cd ²⁺ (-0.4) - Zn ²⁺ (-2.4)/Mn ²⁺ (-3.2)/Ni ²⁺ (-3.0)/Ce ³⁺ (-2.6) Pb ²⁺ (-0.7) - Zn ²⁺ (-2.6)/Mn ²⁺ (-3.5)/Ni ²⁺ (-2.9)/Ce ³⁺ (-2.5) Fe ³⁺ (-0.5) - Zn ²⁺ (-2.2)/Mn ²⁺ (-3.6)/Ni ²⁺ (-2.9)/Ce ³⁺ (-2.5) Cu ²⁺ (-1.0) - Zn ²⁺ (-2.5)/Mn ²⁺ (-3.4)/Ni ²⁺ (-3.0) Au ³⁺ (+1.5) - Pd ²⁺ (+3.7)
0.1 M CH ₃ COOH + 0.1 M CH ₃ COONa (pH 6)	Pd ²⁺ (-4.8) - Co ²⁺ (-1.6)/Ni ²⁺ (-1.5)/Zn ²⁺ (-0.5)/Cd ²⁺ (-0.5)/Mn ²⁺ (-1.5) Hg ²⁺ (+2.2) - Ag ⁺ (0.0)/Cu ²⁺ (-0.5)/Pb ²⁺ (-0.6) Hg ²⁺ (+2.5) - Bi ³⁺ (0.0)/Fe ²⁺ (0.0) UO ₂ ²⁺ (0.8) - Hg ²⁺ (+3.0) Au ³⁺ (0.0) - Pt ⁴⁺ (+2.5) Hg ₂ ²⁺ (0.0) - Hg ²⁺ (+2.5)
0.1 M NH ₄ OH + 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl (pH 8)	VO ²⁺ (0.0) - Hg ²⁺ (+3.8)/P ³⁺ (+3.8)
0.1 M NH ₄ OH + 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl (pH 10)	Pd ²⁺ (-5.3) - Cu ²⁺ (-3.0)/Tl ⁺ (-3.5)

*Data given in parenthesis are average of three runs in each case.

Ag⁺, VO²⁺, Pb²⁺, Tl⁺, Cd²⁺, Pd²⁺ are comparatively low. Pd²⁺ and Cd²⁺ formed chloro-complexes and were strongly adsorbed at pH 2 due to the anion-exchange behaviour of hydrous zirconium oxide, and Ag⁺ was strongly adsorbed and then probably reduced to the metallic state by photochemical reaction. Thus these ions can be separated from numerous metal ions. Some important separations are shown in Table 2. The figures within parentheses denotes the distances migrated by the metal ions (in cm). The above results show that electrophoresis on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper is of value in certain analytical separations of metal ions that are not feasible on ordinary Whatman paper.

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